

Models of *Body-Weight Regulation*

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Set-point, settling-point, and the thrifty and drifty gene hypotheses — and why weight lost is so readily regained.

For clinical understanding, patient education, and interpreting the response to diet, lifestyle and GLP-1–assisted weight loss.

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Why this paper

Patients and clinicians increasingly ask why weight lost on diet or GLP-1 therapy is so hard to keep off, and why the last stretch is the hardest. This paper sets out, with references, the competing scientific models of how body weight is regulated — and is honest that the answer is still contested. It is the reference companion to the clinical article on setting a target waist and weight.

Abstract

Human body weight behaves as though it is regulated, yet the mechanism is disputed. This paper reviews the principal theoretical models — the set-point model, the settling-point (dynamic-equilibrium) model, the family of reconciling models (control-theory, Hall–Guo, operating-point and adiposity-force), and the dual-intervention-point (DIP) model — and then examines the two evolutionary hypotheses proposed to explain why the defended level varies so much between individuals: the thrifty-gene hypothesis and its rival, the drifty-gene hypothesis. It

closes with the evidence that unsettles all of these accounts, including the ambiguous response to withdrawal of GLP-1 receptor agonists. The clinical corollary — that weight loss is easy at first and defended hard below a certain level — is developed in a companion clinical article.

1. Why body weight looks regulated

Over months and years, most adults hold a fairly stable body weight despite eating hundreds of thousands of calories, with intake and expenditure never consciously matched. That stability implies some form of regulation. The unresolved question is *what kind*. Is there an internal reference — a defended target the body actively restores — or does weight simply settle wherever the balance of biology and environment happens to place it? The answer matters, because it shapes what we should expect when someone tries to lose weight, and why the effort so often ends in regain.^[1]

2. The set-point model

The set-point model treats body fat like a thermostat setting: a single reference level is defended by negative feedback.^[1] Its origins lie in the lipostatic hypothesis, which proposed that a circulating signal proportional to fat mass is sensed by the hypothalamus and used to adjust intake.^[2] The signal was given a molecular identity with the discovery of leptin,^[3] secreted by fat and reporting its abundance to the brain.

The model captures the compensations seen during weight loss — rising hunger, falling metabolic rate — elegantly. But it strains against two observations. First, leptin is *high*, not low, in most people living with obesity, and giving extra leptin has little effect except in the rare cases of true deficiency, implying the feedback loop is blunted (“leptin resistance”) rather than simply set high.^[4] Second, and more fundamentally, a tightly defended single point cannot easily explain the obesity epidemic: why would a defended target rise across whole populations within a few decades?^[1]

3. The settling-point (dynamic-equilibrium) model

The settling-point model takes the opposite view: there is no internal reference at all. Because energy expenditure rises with body mass, weight naturally settles at the level where intake and expenditure happen to balance for a given environment. Change the environment — more energy-dense food, less physical effort — and the settling point moves.^[5] The apparent “defence” of a weight is, on this account, an illusion produced by the mathematics of energy balance rather than an active target.^[6]

This model explains the obesity epidemic effortlessly — a changed environment simply moved everyone’s settling point upward. Its difficulty is the mirror image of the set-point model’s: it is less comfortable with the brisk, active compensation people report when they diet, which can feel less like a level quietly re-settling and more like a system pushing back. It is worth noting that the original settling-point formulation did include active control of intake, so the two families of model are not as far apart as their names suggest.^[4]

4. A spectrum of reconciling models

Set-point and settling-point are best seen not as rivals but as the two ends of a continuum of *feedback gain*. Control theory frames it exactly this way: a high-gain feedback system behaves like a set-point, a low-gain one like a settling point, and real biology sits somewhere along the line.^[6] Several formal models occupy the middle ground. The *Hall–Guo model* makes both intake and expenditure depend on body composition, generating realistic weight dynamics; its author regards a set-point-like reading as most consistent with current human data.^[7] The *operating-point model* derives an apparent set-point from the slow dynamics of the leptin system, with hysteresis that can produce a zone of weak regulation.^[8] The *adiposity-force* (“*gravitostat*”) *model* proposes a second, leptin-independent sensor that gauges body weight through mechanical loading on the skeleton.^[9] Notably, each of these can be re-plotted so that its intake or

appetite line splits into upper and lower branches, leaving a gap between them where regulation lapses — the behaviour of the model considered next.^[1]

5. The dual-intervention-point model

The dual-intervention-point (DIP) model replaces the single defended level with two boundaries: an *upper* intervention point (UIP) and a *lower* intervention point (LIP), separated by a broad “zone of indifference” in which the body reacts weakly, if at all, to changes in fatness.^[10] Regulation switches on strongly only when a boundary is crossed. The evolutionary logic is that two different threats set the two boundaries: the risk of starvation and disease historically defended the lower point, while the risk of predation defended the upper one.^[10]
^[11]

Because the two points are independent, the model naturally accommodates individual variation: two people with the same lower point but different upper points will, in an energy-rich environment, come to rest at very different weights. This is the feature that makes the DIP model attractive clinically, and it is the “two set-points” framing many practitioners find most intuitive. Figure 1 contrasts it with the set-point and settling-point models.

Figure 1. (a) The set-point model defends a single level by negative feedback. (b) The settling-point model has no internal reference; weight settles where intake meets expenditure and moves with the environment. (c) The dual-intervention-point model has an upper and a lower boundary with a “zone of indifference” between; regulation is weak within the zone and strong outside it,

with the lower boundary defended most fiercely. Schematic only; axes conceptual and not to scale.

6. Where does the variation come from? Thrifty versus drift genes

If people carry different upper boundaries, the obvious question is why. Two evolutionary hypotheses compete to explain it. The *thrifty-gene hypothesis* proposes that recurrent famine actively selected for alleles that store fat efficiently: in a feast-or-famine world, thrifty individuals survived and reproduced, so fat-storing genes spread — only to become harmful in modern abundance.^[12] It is an intuitive story, and for decades it was the default explanation.

The *drifty-gene hypothesis* challenges it on the numbers.^[13] Famines are relatively recent and infrequent, and their mortality falls mainly on the very young and very old rather than selectively on the lean, so the selective pressure they exert on fat-storage genes is probably too weak to account for modern obesity. In its place, the hypothesis proposes an absence of selection. For our early ancestors, predators enforced a firm upper limit on fatness — a slow, heavy animal is an easy meal. Around two million years ago, fire, weapons and social organisation largely removed that predation risk. With the upper boundary no longer under selective pressure, the genes defining it were free to accumulate random mutations and *drift*, producing today's wide spread of upper intervention points, while the lower point stayed under the enduring pressure of starvation and disease.^{[13][14]}

The two hypotheses make different predictions about the shape of the population. Selection for thrift would tend to shift the whole distribution of fatness upward; drift acting only on the upper boundary would instead skew it to the right, with a long tail of susceptible individuals above a relatively fixed floor (Figure 2). The observed distribution of body fatness is markedly right-skewed, and the weakness of selection signatures at obesity-associated genetic variants is more consistent with drift than with strong positive selection.^{[14][15]}

Figure 2. Contrasting predictions. Under the thrifty-gene hypothesis, positive selection for fat storage shifts the whole population distribution of fatness upward. Under the drifty-gene hypothesis, only the upper intervention point drifts, leaving the lower boundary fixed and producing a right-skewed distribution with a long tail of susceptible individuals. The observed distribution of human fatness is right-skewed. Schematic only; curves illustrative.

7. Evidence that unsettles every model

No model accounts for all the observations, and intellectual honesty requires stating the difficulties plainly.^[1] *The timing problem:* if drift in the upper point was largely complete tens of thousands of years ago, why did obesity become common only recently? The usual answer — that food was simply never abundant enough — sits awkwardly beside evidence of prehistoric population growth, the rapid over-hunting of large herbivores, and Palaeolithic figurines depicting bodies living with obesity.^[1]

Captive animals: many animals grow fat in captivity despite an evolutionary history entirely unlike ours, suggesting either that the upper point is flexible to perceived predation risk or that shared environmental factors dominate.^[1]

Resistance to loss within the zone: the DIP model predicts indifference between the two points, yet people well above their presumed lower point still show hunger and metabolic slowing when they diet. One repair — that rising adiposity drags the lower point upward — rescues the phenomenon but makes little evolutionary sense.^[1] A more radical reading is that these compensations are not “defence of a set level of fat” at all, but simply the body’s response to an

immediate energy shortfall — behaviour that merely *resembles* set-point defence.^[1] That these adaptations can persist for years after weight loss is well documented,^{[16][17]} but persistence alone does not distinguish the two interpretations.

The GLP-1 withdrawal test: withdrawing an appetite-suppressing GLP-1 receptor agonist offers a natural experiment. In the STEP 1 extension, participants regained about two-thirds of their lost weight in the year after stopping semaglutide, and modelling of the rebound was consistent with reactive over-eating — a set-point-like defence.^[18] Yet in STEP 4, participants switched to placebo after a shorter run-in simply drifted back toward baseline intake without overshooting — a settling-point-like pattern.^[19] The two experiments point in opposite directions, and neither model comfortably accommodates both.^[1]

8. Clinical corollary

Whichever model proves closest to the truth, the practical pattern is consistent and worth stating: weight often comes off readily at first and is then defended more stubbornly below a certain level, differing person to person. The two-point framing captures this most intuitively — early loss traverses a zone of weak regulation, later loss meets a defended lower boundary — while remaining agnostic about the deeper mechanism. It is the framing this author leans on in the clinic — though it must be said plainly that the dual-intervention-point model, like every account described here, is an *unproven working hypothesis*, not established fact. How this shapes the setting of a realistic target waist and weight, with or without a GLP-1 medicine, is developed in the companion clinical article.^[20]

9. Conclusion

The set-point and settling-point models are best understood as two ends of a continuum, and the reconciling models — control-theory, Hall–Guo, operating-

point, adiposity-force and the dual-intervention-point — are variations on how to blend them. The drifty-gene hypothesis supplies a plausible, if unproven, account of why the upper boundary varies so widely between individuals, and improves on the older thrifty-gene idea on several counts. But no single model explains the totality of the evidence, and the contradictory responses to GLP-1 withdrawal show how much remains open. The honest position is that body-weight regulation is still being mapped, and the discriminating experiments are sorely needed.^[1]

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This white paper is intended as an educational resource for patients and clinicians. The models it describes are competing scientific hypotheses under active debate, not established fact, and it is not a diagnostic instrument. The figures are schematic illustrations of concepts and are not derived from any specific dataset. This document does not constitute individual medical advice; all decisions should be made in the context of full clinical assessment and professional judgement.

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